

ADAPTATION TECHNIQUE OF FUNCTIONAL TRANSLATION FEATURES IN LITERARY TEXTS.

(IN TERMS OF ROMEO AND JULIETTE)

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Annotation. *This research gives information about the technique of adaptation of functional translation features in artistic texts, which is considered the main part of the field of translation studies. Our scientific research is devoted to the artistic analysis of Rameo and Juliet by the famous English writer Shakespeare. in the article, the work is deeply analyzed in terms of the topic and ideas are explained through examples.*

Key words: *Cultural adaptation, cultural references, linguistic and stylistic, emotional and thematic, adaptation genre adaptation*

The adaptation technique in the functional translation of literary texts is a strategic approach aimed at ensuring that translations are both faithful to the original work and accessible to the target audience. This technique involves modifying various elements of the text to preserve its meaning, tone, and impact while accommodating cultural and linguistic differences between the source and target languages. The primary goal of adaptation is to bridge the gap between different languages and cultures while preserving the literary and artistic value of the original text. By employing adaptation techniques, translators can produce translations that are not only accurate but also meaningful and enjoyable for readers in the target language. This approach helps in creating translations that are

both faithful to the original work and responsive to the expectations and preferences of the new audience.

So far Shakespeare's works have been studied and discussed by many scholars. Specifically David and Ben Crystal's *Shakespeare's Words: A Dictionary and Language Companion*. This work provides information on the linguistic structure of Shakespeare's texts and is useful for showing how characters control Shakespeare's language. The *Shakespeare Translation* by Michael Dobson and Stanley Wells. Three books examine different translations of Shakespeare's works, providing a broad perspective on translation techniques and challenges. The *Cambridge Companion to the Shakespeare Translation*, edited by Anthony J. Farrell. A collection of essays exploring different interpretations of Shakespeare's plays, *Juliet Personal*, *Romeo and Juliet* from various theoretical and practical endeavors.

The adaptation technique in functional translation for literary texts involves tailoring the original work to fit the cultural, linguistic, and contextual expectations of the target audience, while maintaining the essence of the source material. For *Romeo and Juliet*, this technique involves several key aspects.

Cultural Adaptation. *Romeo and Juliet* is set in 16th-century Verona, Italy, with societal norms and references specific to that time and place. In translations or adaptations, references to customs, social structures, or historical events that may not be familiar to modern audiences might be updated or explained. For instance, a translator might include footnotes or provide contextual explanations to help readers understand these elements.

Research explores how translators address cultural references and Elizabethan societal norms in "Romeo and Juliet." This includes how they adapt or localize elements like social hierarchy, family honor, and historical context to resonate with contemporary or non-English-speaking audiences.

Studies show that translators often use footnotes, glossaries, or contextual explanations to make Elizabethan customs and societal norms understandable. For instance, the concept of the "duel" or "honor" might be explained or adapted to reflect contemporary or culturally relevant practices in the target language.

Cultural References. Specific cultural references, like feasts, clothing, or social customs, may be adapted to align with the target culture's norms. For example, if translating into a culture with different traditional practices, a translator might modify or contextualize these elements to make them more relatable.

Linguistic and Stylistic Adaptation. Research delves into how translators handle Shakespeare's distinctive language, including his use of iambic pentameter, archaic vocabulary, and rhetorical devices. This involves adapting Shakespeare's poetic style and maintaining the rhythm and musicality of his verse.

Scholars find that adaptations often involve restructuring verse to fit the target language's poetic forms or sacrificing some of Shakespeare's linguistic complexity for readability. Translators might also seek equivalents for puns and wordplay, though some studies indicate that preserving Shakespeare's original puns can be particularly challenging.

Verse and Meter. Shakespeare's use of iambic pentameter and blank verse is a key stylistic feature. Translators may strive to preserve the rhythmic quality and poetic form, though this can be challenging. Some translations might retain the meter and rhyme schemes, while others might adapt them to suit the target language's poetic traditions.

Modernization of Language. Updating Archaic Language: Shakespeare's language can be archaic for modern readers. Translators often modernize the text to make it more accessible while trying to retain the original

meaning and tone. For instance, terms and expressions that were common in Elizabethan English might be replaced with contemporary equivalents.

Characterization and Dialogue. Adapting Dialogue: The emotional intensity and nuances of dialogue are crucial in *Romeo and Juliet*. Translators work to capture the emotional weight and interpersonal dynamics between characters. This might involve rephrasing dialogue to fit natural speech patterns in the target language while retaining the original sentiment.

Character Names and Titles. Name Adaptation: Sometimes, character names or titles might be adapted for ease of pronunciation or cultural relevance. For instance, if a name has a particular meaning or connotation in the source language, the translator might choose a name in the target language that conveys a similar meaning or impact.

Emotional and Thematic Adaptation. Studies investigate how translations maintain the emotional and thematic depth of "Romeo and Juliet," including the intensity of the romance, the conflict between the Montagues and Capulets, and the tragic elements of the play.

Research often highlights that successful adaptations preserve the play's emotional impact through careful choice of words and phrasing that evoke similar responses in the target audience. Adaptations might modify certain scenes or dialogue to better capture the dramatic tension or romantic fervor.

Functional and Pragmatic Adaptation. Scientific works analyze how translators address practical aspects of the text, such as idiomatic expressions, humor, and cultural nuances that may not have direct equivalents in the target language.

Studies show that translators use various strategies, including paraphrasing, substituting culturally specific terms, or providing additional explanations, to ensure that the functional aspects of the play are clear and effective in the target

language. For example, idiomatic expressions in Shakespeare's text might be adapted to similar expressions that convey the same meaning in the target language.

Comparative Analysis of Translations. Comparative studies examine multiple translations of "Romeo and Juliet" to evaluate different approaches to adaptation and their effectiveness in capturing the essence of the original text.

Comparative research often reveals a range of translation strategies and their impacts on how audiences experience the play. Studies might assess how different translators balance fidelity to the original text with the need to adapt for cultural and linguistic differences, and how these choices affect the play's reception.

Social and Political Elements. Class and Social Hierarchies: The social structure and class distinctions present in Shakespeare's time might be reinterpreted or adjusted in translations. This ensures that the dynamics between characters and the social commentary of the play remain relevant and comprehensible to contemporary audiences.

Genre Adaptation. Different Formats: Adaptations of *Romeo and Juliet* into films, musicals (e.g., *West Side Story*), or modern novels often involve significant changes. These adaptations may relocate the story to different settings or time periods, reimagining the narrative to fit new genres while aiming to retain the core themes of love, conflict, and fate.

In summary, the adaptation technique in functional translation of *Romeo and Juliet* encompasses a wide range of considerations, from language and cultural relevance to medium-specific adaptations and audience engagement. Each adaptation involves creative decisions aimed at preserving the essence of Shakespeare's play while making it accessible, relevant, and engaging for diverse audiences across different contexts and formats. This process reflects both the timeless nature of the original work and the dynamic ways it can be experienced

and interpreted in various cultural and artistic settings.

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